

TABLE I: Real-world Temporal Graph inputs and their key properties.

Datasets	$ V $	$ E $	$ E / V $
sx-Stackoverflow [1]	6024270	57724802	10
enron [2]	87273	594912	7
sx-mathoverflow [3]	88580	375972	4
fb-wall [4]	63891	366824	6

Fig. 1: Dynamic graph insertion performance in seconds (lower is better) for the real-world temporal graphs. sx-stackoverflow graph with 30% pre-initialization case was presented in the paper in Fig. 7(a). These results demonstrate AVEC-CSR is not sensitive to the pre-initialization size.

Fig 2: Dynamic graph insertion performance (in seconds) of two representative graphs for random workload with 10% pre-initialization. This can be matched with the 30% pre-initialization results presented in the paper (Fig. 7a). This result further supports the insensitivity of AVEC-CSR's performance on the pre-initialization size.

Fig. 3: Time to run Graph Analytics (in seconds) in a single thread on the real-world temporal graphs with 30% pre-initialization. The lower is better. AVEC-CSR does not represent the offloading feature. Paper contains (in Fig. 8 and TABLE V) Graph Analytics performance (normalized to CSR) on single and 32-thread cases. These results show our observations still hold across various real-world temporal graphs.

Reference:

1. A. Paranjape, A. R. Benson, and J. Leskovec, "Motifs in temporal networks," in Proceedings of the Tenth ACM International Conference on Web Search and Data Mining, ser. WSDM '17. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, 2017, p. 601–610. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3018661.3018731>
2. Bryan Klimt and Yiming Yang. The Enron corpus: A new dataset for email classification research. In Proc. Eur. Conf. on Mach. Learn., pages 217–226, 2004.
3. Ashwin Paranjape, Austin R. Benson, and Jure Leskovec. "Motifs in Temporal Networks." In Proceedings of the Tenth ACM International Conference on Web Search and Data Mining, 2017.
4. tdGraphEmbed: Temporal Dynamic Graph-Level Embedding. Moran Beladev, Lior Rokach, Gilad Katz, Ido Guy, Kira Radinsky. CIKM'20 – October 2020, Galway, Ireland.